

The Influence of Anthropometric Characteristics on Punch Impact

Abstract

Introduction: Certain anthropometric characteristics, such as height and weight, can influence the punch impact force of striking combat sport athletes, affecting their strategies and punch choices. Although height is often considered relevant for combat strategy, the relationship between these characteristics and athletic success remains inconclusive. **Methods:** Research was conducted using the electronic databases PubMed, SPORTDiscus and Web of Science, considering studies to date that reported participants' anthropometric characteristics related to punch impact analysis. The search resulted in 1859 potential studies, of which 23 met the inclusion criteria and were included in this literature review. **Results:** A total of 381 participants (men = 304; women = 30; unknown = 47) were part of the 23 included studies. The most used instruments to measure impact force were those with load cells inserted in wall bags and force platforms with padded targets. The Cross and Rear Hook punches were highlighted as those generating the most impact force, ranging from 2622 ± 288 to 5008.6 ± 76.3 N. Regarding measuring impact power, the most used instrument was the PowerKube, with the Cross punch producing the highest impact power, averaging between 15183.27 ± 4368.90 and 22014 ± 1336 W. Most studies were rated as having "moderate" methodological quality ($k = 21$) due to study design, low sample power, and lack of representativeness. Only two studies were considered of "strong" quality. **Discussion/Conclusion:** Various studies have attempted to identify which punch generates the most impact, but the absence of a Gold Standard and the variety of instruments result in varying impact force values, from 544 to 6860 N. Although height is cited as an important factor in punch choice and effectiveness, this review could not confirm that relationship. The review emphasizes the importance of future studies standardizing evaluation instruments to analyze different punches reliably, which will contribute to the advancement of striking combat sports.

Keywords: Combat Sport; Punch; Anthropometric Characteristics; Impact Force; Impact Power.

1-Introduction

Empirically, certain anthropometric characteristics, particularly height, have been referred to as crucial for the technical profile of striking combat sport athletes, influencing their combat strategies. It has been demonstrated that the choice of technical attack punch depends on distance, position, and movement relative to the target (Hristovski et al., 2006; Lenetsky et al., 2022). However, although height is considered important in combat strategy, its relationship with victory is still inconclusive (Davis et al., 2016; Pic, 2017).

The literature on the technical component analysis of combat sports that use punch, is diverse but inconclusive. In the last two decades, the technical profile of athletes and the variables influencing their choices during movement execution have been analyzed (Davis et al., 2016; Hristovski et al., 2006). In this context, most striking combat sports punches can be divided into three types: (a) Straight punches, predominantly performed with the fists in the frontal direction; (b) Hook punches, actions with the fists performed predominantly in lateral movements; (c) Uppercut punches, actions with the fists predominantly in vertical movements (Hristovski et al., 2006).

To increase the likelihood of ending a match by incapacitating the opponent, the impact generated by punches has been widely analyzed (Chaabène et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2018; Smith, 2006). The effectiveness of punch impact is a complex movement involving the upper and lower body muscles and the proper cooperation of agonist and antagonist muscles (Ebben & Blackard, 1997; Filimonov et al., 1985; Giovani & Nikolaidis, 2012; Joch et al., 1981; Lenetsky et al., 2013; Loturco et al., 2016; McGill et al., 2010). Filimonov et al. (1985) referred to three main components for generating impact in rear-hand boxing punches: (a) the contribution of the arm muscles to the target, (b) the rotation of the trunk, and (c) the push-off from the legs (Filimonov et al., 1985). Similarly, Ruddock et al. (2016) mentioned three factors contributing to the effectiveness of a boxing punch: (a) the speed of muscle group synergy activation, (b) the arm's momentum, and (c) the muscular activation at the moment of impact to effectively transfer the displaced mass, referred to as "stiffening" (Ruddock et al., 2016).

Additionally, there is evidence showing variations in impact levels among specific punches, different weight categories, and the limb length of athletes (Podhurskyi, 2020; Tiwari et al., 2021). According to the literature, there are three types of punch impact assessment in combat sports athletes: (a) Direct inertia-relevant assessment, with cells

and platforms directly connected to the target, providing a direct measure of the impact applied during the punch (e.g., force platforms); (b) Indirect inertia-relevant assessment, which involves indirect measurement of impact, such as calculating changes in target acceleration caused by the impact instead of measuring the force directly (e.g., changing the bag's movement through slow-motion observation); (c) Impact assessment on the athlete's limb, such as a fist, using measurement devices (e.g., load cells in boxing gloves) (Lenetsky et al., 2022).

Moreover, different studies have emerged to measure punch impact using units of force (N), power (W), velocity (m/s), acceleration (m/s^2), gravitational acceleration (g), and mass (kg) (Atha et al., 1985; Beattie & Ruddock, 2022; Brown et al., 2022; Girodet et al., 2005; Pierce et al., 2006; Smith, 2006; Tiwari et al., 2021; Walilko et al., 2005). The International System of Units for force is the newton (N), and although many studies analyze the impact force of a punch in newtons, the dynamic nature of punches requires measuring impact power in watts (W) (Del Vecchio et al., 2022; Powers & Howley, 1995). Power describes the amount of work performed per unit of time (Powers & Howley, 1995). This concept seems crucial for evaluating the intensity and effectiveness of a punch, as it directly relates to the applied force and the punch's execution speed (Del Vecchio et al., 2022).

The aim of this systematic review is to verify the state of the art concerning the analysis of the influence of anthropometric characteristics on the impact generated by punches. The studies included in this review cover periods between the 2000s and 2020.

2-Methods

This systematic literature review was prepared according to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) statement (Page et al., 2021).

2.1-Eligibility Criteria

All studies published to date reporting participants' anthropometric characteristics (e.g., height, weight) related to punch impact analysis in Newton (N) or Watts (W) units were included. All study types were considered for inclusion in the review, except qualitative studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses. This review was limited to articles published in English.

2.2-Search Strategy The search was conducted using the electronic databases PubMed, SPORTDiscus and Web of Science to identify and select relevant studies for inclusion in this review, combining three sets of terms: (i) terms related to the population of interest; (ii) terms related to anthropometric characteristics; (iii) terms related to punches. The following combination of terms was used for the search: (boxing OR combat sports OR muay thai OR kickboxing OR karate OR mma OR kung fu) AND (height OR anthropometric characteristics OR body measurements OR anthropometry OR physical Attributes) AND (punch OR strength OR impact force OR power OR performance OR activity profile OR punch performance). The search was performed on August 30, 2024. Additionally, a manual search of the literature cited in articles and reference journals was conducted.

2.3-Study Selection, Data Extraction, and Synthesis

The articles resulting from the search were initially identified as potentially eligible based on their titles and abstracts. After a full reading and based on the eligibility criteria, the articles for this review were selected. Zotero for Windows was used to manage the references.

A specific form was developed for data extraction, including information on:

- i. **Study characteristics:** authors, year of publication, and design;
- ii. **Sample characteristics:** size, gender, age, height, weight, weight index (BMI);
- iii. **Type of sport;**
- iv. **Variables of interest** (types of technical gestures analyzed);
- v. **Measuring instruments;**
- vi. **Main results.**

The qualitative synthesis of the data was presented in table format. The extracted characteristics and variables are organized by study, in alphabetical order (Tables 1 and 2).

2.4-Quality Assessment of the Studies

To assess the quality of the included studies, an adapted version of the Quality Assessment Tool for Quantitative Studies from the Effective Public Health Practice Project (Thomas et al., 2004) was used, recommended by the Cochrane Public Health Review Group (Higgins et al., 2011) and previously applied by Teixeira et al. (2015). This tool allows for the evaluation of the quality of experimental and observational studies across eight domains: representativeness (selection bias); study design; confounding factors; blinding;

data collection; data analysis; presentation of results; and representativeness (exclusions/dropouts). Each domain is rated as strong (good methodological quality), moderate, or weak (poor methodological quality), with the final assessment determined according to the ratings in each domain.

3-Results

3.1-Description of Included Studies

The literature search conducted using the PubMed, SPORTDiscus and Web of Science databases resulted in 1849 potential studies (Figure 1). Subsequently, 10 studies were added manually. Of the 1859 initially identified studies, 68 were removed as duplicates. 1749 studies were excluded based on title and abstract. The primary reasons for exclusion in this phase were that the articles did not reference the anthropometric characteristics of the sample or did not present results of interest to the review (Magnitude of punch impact). Additionally, qualitative studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses were excluded at this stage. As a result, 42 articles were considered potentially eligible for full-text reading. After reviewing the full texts of the selected articles, 23 were found to meet the inclusion criteria and were included in this literature review.

Figure 1 | Flow diagram according to PRISMA 2020 standards (Page et al. 2021).

3.2-Study Characteristics

Tables 1 and 2 detail the characteristics of the studies included in this analysis. The majority of the studies ($k = 18$) had a cross-sectional observational design, three studies had an experimental design, and two were quasi-experimental.

3.3-Participant Characteristics

A total of 381 participants (men = 304; women = 30; unknown = 47) were part of the 23 included studies (Tables 1 and 2). The mean age of these samples ranged from 17.5 ± 0.5 to 47.5 ± 10.13 years, with an mean height between 172 ± 10 and 182 ± 5 cm, and weight ranging from 64.56 ± 12.1 to 86.8 ± 17 kg.

3.4-Impact Force

Regarding impact force, a total of 262 participants (men = 186; women = 29; unknown = 47) were part of the 16 studies included (Table 1). The mean age of these samples ranged from 17.5 ± 0.5 to 47.5 ± 10.13 years, height ranged from 172 ± 10 to 182 ± 5 cm, and weight ranged from 64.56 ± 12.1 to 86.8 ± 17 kg. Most studies reported higher impact force values for the rear hand Straight punch (Adamec et al., 2021; Buško et al., 2016; V. A. de Souza & Marques, 2017; V. de Souza & Marques, 2017; Dyson et al., 2005; Kim et al., 2018; Lee & McGill, 2017; Loturco et al., 2016; Smith, 2006; Smith et al., 2000; Walilko et al., 2005). However, some studies indicated that the rear hand Hook punch has a greater impact force (Dunn et al., 2019, 2022; Finlay et al., 2022). To simplify the various terminologies presented in the literature, we opted to define the force measuring devices reflected in this review (e.g., dynamometer, load cell, force sensor) as load cells, as this is the most common definition in the literature and simplifies interpretation, given that all these devices are specific instruments for measuring force. Accordingly, we identified the following 10 different instruments: (1) Accelerometer embedded in the dummy's head and in the participants' gloves; (2) Tri-axial accelerometer embedded in the dummy's head; (3) Target with embedded accelerometer and load cell; (4) Target with boxing-specific load cell and force transducer; (5) Target on a board with a side load cell, transducer, and corresponding software; (6) Load cell embedded in the wall-mounted bag, with transducer and corresponding software; (7) Load cell embedded in the target, with transducer and corresponding software; (8) Load cell embedded in the punching bag, with transducer and corresponding software; (9) Force platform with padded target; (10) Punching bag with embedded load cell and

gyroscope transducer. In this context, to facilitate the analysis of impact force data, we included studies that presented values in Newton (N) units, identifying the highest impact force values by instrument (Figure 2), as well as the type of instrument and key results (Table 2).

Figure 2 | Highest Impact Force Values by Instrument

Legend:

- **Accelerometer and Load Cell** = Target with an accelerometer and load cell inserted;
- **Accelerometer and Gloves** = Accelerometer inserted in the dummy's head and the participants' gloves;
- **Tri-axial Accelerometers** = Tri-axial accelerometers inserted in the dummy's head;
- **Specific Load Cell** = Target with a load cell specific to boxing and force transducer;
- **Load Cell in Wall Bag** = Load cell inserted in the wall bag, with transducer and respective software;
- **Load Cell in Target** = Load cell inserted in the target, with transducer and respective software;
- **Load Cell in Boxing Bag** = Load cell inserted in the boxing bag, with transducer and respective software;
- **Force Platform** = Force platform with cushioned target;
- **Boxing Bag with Load Cell and Gyroscope** = Boxing bag with load cell and an inserted gyroscope transducer;

- **Board with Load Cell** = Target on a board with a lateral load cell, transducer, and respective software.

3.5-Impact Power

Regarding impact power, a total of 119 participants (men = 118; women = 1) were included in the 7 studies (Table 2). The mean age of these samples ranged from 24 ± 4 to 29.0 ± 2.0 years, the mean height ranged from 176.7 ± 6.2 to 181.72 ± 8.28 cm, and weight ranged from 76.0 ± 7.2 to 80.9 ± 12.24 kg. The studies only evaluated Straight punches, where the Cross (Straight punch from the rear hand) consistently presented higher values than the Jab (Straight punch from the front hand).

The studies analyzing power used only two instruments, the PowerKube and StrikeMate, which are similar with small differences (name and appearance). The PowerKube replaced the StrikeMate, and both are from the same manufacturer (Del Vecchio et al., 2022). The device in question is a portable and lightweight impact cube, specifically designed to measure and analyze impact power and direction. It has a compact design and weighs only 3 kg. Inside the cube are two high-precision accelerometers, responsible for detecting and quantifying the acceleration caused by impacts. These sensors convert the mechanical energy of the impact into electrical signals, which are then processed by specialized software. This software, developed specifically for this device, collects the raw data from the accelerometers and transforms it into useful and comprehensible information. Through complex analyses, it is possible to determine the exact power of the impact in Watts, the direction in which it occurred, and other relevant parameters (Del Vecchio et al., 2021).

3.7-Synthesis of Results

All studies ($k = 23$) mention at least one of the anthropometric characteristics of the participants (Tables 1 and 2). Regarding impact force, the most commonly used instruments in the studies were those with load cells inserted in the wall bag, equipped with transducers and appropriate software ($k=3$), and force platforms with cushioned targets ($k=3$). Both instruments, which are methods of direct relevant inertia evaluation, showed the punches with the highest values, particularly the Cross and the Rear Hook, with an mean impact force ranging from 1331.67 ± 234.49 to 5008.6 ± 76.3 N (Table 1). The instrument that

demonstrated the highest impact force values was the one with load cells inserted in the wall bag (Figure 2 and Table 1).

Regarding impact power, all studies used the same type of direct relevant inertia evaluation instrument. This instrument identified the Cross as the punch with the highest value, with an mean impact power ranging from 15183.27 ± 4368.90 to 22014 ± 1336 W (Table 2).

3.8-Methodological Quality of the Studies

Tables 3 and 4 present the methodological quality of the studies. Most studies (k=21) were rated as having "moderate" methodological quality due to the study design, low sample power, and lack of representativeness of the population studied. Two studies were rated as having "strong" methodological quality.

Tabela 1 Characteristics of participants, type of sport, techniques, instruments, mean and maximum impact force in Newton (N) units of measurement.

Reference	Study design	Participants	Type of sport	Variables of interest	Instruments	Main results
(Adamec et al., 2021)	Cross-sectional	N = 50 (men = 29; women = 21); Age: 34 years; Height: 174 cm; Weight: 76 kg.	Karate.	Straight punch from dominant and non-dominant hand.	Force platform with cushioned target (DIRA).	Fmax - Straight punch (4639 N).
(Buško et al., 2016)	Cross-sectional	N = 13 men; Age: 17.5 years; Height: 175.5 cm; Weight: 69kg.	Boxing.	Jab, Cross.	Boxing bag with load cell and an inserted gyroscope transducer (DIRA).	Fmean - Cross (1592,5 ± 507,1 N).
(Chadli et al., 2014)	Cross-sectional	N = 11 (unknown gender); Age: 23.5 ± 0.5 years; Height: 179 ± 9 cm; Weight: 77.39 ± 11 kg.	Boxing.	Punch (not specified).	Target with an accelerometer and load cell inserted (DIRA).	Fmean - Punch (989 ± 116,76 N).
(Dunn et al., 2019)	Cross-sectional	N = 15 men; Age: 17.5 ± 0.5 years; Height: 177.5 ± 9 cm; Weight: 73 ± 14 kg.	Boxing.	Straights and Hooks punch.	Load cell inserted in the wall bag, with transducer and respective software (DIRA).	Fmean - Jabs (841 ± 180 N); Cross (1818 ± 332 N); Hooks (2622 ± 288 N).
(Dunn et al., 2022)	Cross-sectional	N = 28 men; Age: 19 ± 2 years; Height: 177 ± 7.3 cm; Weight: 70,5 ± 11 kg.	Boxing.	Straights and Hooks punch of both hands.	Load cell inserted in the wall bag, with transducer and respective software (DIRA).	Fmean - Jab (823 ± 271 N); Cross (1830 ± 387 N); Front hand hook (2491 ± 492 N); Back hand hook (2742 ± 571 N).

(Dyson et al., 2005)	Cross-sectional	N = 6 men; Age: 24.5 ± 3.3 years; Height: 182 ± 5 cm; Weight: 73.3 ± 19 kg.	Boxing.	Jab, Cross.	Load cell inserted in the boxing bag, with transducer and respective software (DIRA).	Fmean - Cross (4236 ± 181 N); Jab (2722±75 N).
(Finlay, 2022)	Experimental	N = 10 men; Age: 19.7 ± 1.2 years; Height: 180.9 ± 7.0 cm; Weight: 78.7 ± 9.6 kg.	Boxing.	Straights and Hooks punch.	Force platform with cushioned target (DIRA).	Fmax - Back hand hook (2673 N); Front hand hook (2565 N); Cross (2538 N).
(Kim et al., 2018)	Quasi-experimental	N = 15 men; Age: 23.4 years; Height: 176.5 cm; Weight: 67.7 kg.	Boxing.	Cross.	Tri-axial accelerometers inserted in the dummy's head (DIRA).	Fmax - Cross (2313 N).
(Lee & McGill, 2017)	Quasi-experimental	N = 12 men; Age: 24.2 ± 2.9 years; Height: 180 ± 5 cm; Weight: 76.8 ± 9.7 kg.	Muay Thai.	Jab, Cross, Joelho.	Load cell inserted in the wall bag, with transducer and respective software (DIRA).	Fmean - Jab (3093.7 ± 69.4 N); Cross (5008.6 ± 76.3 N); Knee (9482 ± 152.8 N).
(Loturco et al., 2016)	Cross-sectional	N = 15 (men = 9; women = 6); Age: 25.9 ± 4.7years; Height: 172 ± 10 cm; Weight: 64.56 ± 12.1 kg.	Boxing.	Jab, Cross.	Force platform with cushioned target (DIRA).	Fmean - Jab men (1152.22 ± 246.87 N); Cross men (1331.67 ± 234.49 N); Jab women (902.50±213.49 N); Cross women (994.17±221.14 N).
(Neto et al., 2009)	Cross-sectional	N = 12 (men = 10; women = 2); Age: 23.4 years; Height: 174.7 ± 4 cm;	Kung Fu.	Punch (not specified).	Load cell inserted in the target, with transducer and respective software (DIRA).	Fmax - Punch (1226 N).

(Smith et al., 2000)	Cross-sectional	Weight: 70.9 ± 12 kg. N = 23 men; Age: 23.1 ± 1.2 years; Height: 178 ± 6 cm;	Boxing.	Jab, Cross.	Target with a load cell specific to boxing and force transducer (DIRA).	Fmean - Cross – Elite (4800 ± 227 N), intermediate (3722 ± 133 N), beginner (2381 ± 116 N).
(Smith, 2006)	Cross-sectional	Weight: 69.9 ± 8.6 kg. N = 29 (unknown gender); Age: 21 ± 2 years; Height: 174 ± 8 cm;	Boxing.	Straights with both hands to the face and torso, Hooks with both hands to the face and torso.	Target with a load cell specific to boxing and force transducer (DIRA).	Fmean - Jab to the face (1722 ± 700 N), to the body (1682 ± 636 N); Cross to the face (2643 ± 1273 N), to the body (2646 ± 1083 N); Front hand hook to the face (2412 ± 813 N), to the body (2414 ± 718 N); Back hand hook to the face (2588 ± 1040 N), to the body (2555 ± 926 N).
(V. A. de Souza & Marques, 2017)	Cross-sectional	Weight: 67 ± 10 kg. N = 8 men; Age: 20.25 ± 4.13 years; Height: 174 ± 4 cm;	Karate.	Straights (gyakuzuki).	Target on a board with a lateral load cell, transducer, and respective software (DIRA).	Fmax - Straight punch (1812.01 N).
(V. de Souza & Marques, 2017)	Cross-sectional	Weight: 72.41 ± 9.6 kg. N = 8 men; Age: 47.5 ± 10.13 years; Height: 176 ± 3 cm;	Karate.	Straights (gyakuzuki).	Target on a board with a lateral load cell, transducer, and respective software (DIRA).	Fmean - Straight punch (2260.79 ± 538.44 N).
(Walilko et al., 2005)	Cross-sectional	Weight: 86.8 ± 17 kg. N = 7 (unknown gender); Weight: 48 a 109kg.	Boxing.	Straights.	Accelerometer inserted in the dummy's head and the participants' gloves (DIRA e AL).	Fmax - Straight punch (3427 N). Weight categories: Flyweight (3914 N); Light welterweight (3621 N); Middleweight (3072 N); Super heavyweight (4741 N).

DIRA = Direct inertia-relevant assessment; AL = Assessment on the athlete's limb; Jab = Straight punch with the front hand; Cross = Straight punch with the back hand; Fmax = Maximum punch force; Fmean = Mean punch force.

Tabela 2 Characteristics of participants, type of sport, techniques, instruments, mean and maximum impact power in Watts (W) units of measurement.

Reference	Study design	Participants	Type of sport	Variables of interest	Instruments	Main results
(Brown et al., 2020)	Cross-sectional	N = 15 men; Age: 24.2 ± 2.9 years; Height: 176.7 ± 6.2 cm; Weight: 79.3 ± 11.8 kg; BMI: 24.9 kg.m-2.	Boxing	Jab; Cross.	PowerKube (DIRA).	Pmean - Cross (15227.4 ± 225 W).
(Brown et al., 2021)	Experimental	N = 20 men; Age: 28 ± 6 years; Height: 178 ± 4 cm; Weight: 76.5 ± 10 kg.	Boxing.	Cross.	PowerKube (DIRA).	Pmean - Cross (22014 ± 1336 W).
(Brown et al., 2022)	Cross-sectional	N = 22 men; Age: 28 ± 2 years; Height: 178 ± 8.1 cm; Weight: 79 ± 7.1 kg; BMI: 24.9 ± 2.5 kg.m-2.	Boxing	Cross.	PowerKube (DIRA).	Pmean - Cross (15227 ± 2250 W).
(Brown et al., 2023)	Cross-sectional	N = 16 (men = 15; women = 1); Age: 24 ± 4 years; Height: 181.72 ± 8.28 cm; Weight: 80.16 ± 11.32 kg.	Boxing; Muay Thai	Cross.	PowerKube (DIRA).	Pmean - Cross (19640 ± 1410 W).
(Del Vecchio et al., 2018)	Experimental	N = 17 men (10 EG; 6 CG);	Combat sports (not specified)	Jab; Cross; Front kick;	StrikeMate (DIRA).	Pmean - Jab (6781.6 ± 2178.9 W); Cross (15335.9 ± 4432.8 W); Front kick (8357.5 ± 2895.9 W); Roundhouse kick (40129.2 ± 10169.8 W).

		Age: 28 ± 2 (EG) e 29 ± 2 (CG) years;		Roundhouse kick.		
		Height: 178 ± 8.1 (EG) e 177.7 ± 5.7 (CG) cm;				
		Weight: 79 ± 7.1 (EG) e 79.8 ± 11.9 (CG) kg.				
(Del Vecchio et al., 2019)	Experimental	N = 16 men (10 EG; 6 CG); Age: 25.2 ± 1.8 (EG) e 29 ± 2 (CG) years; Height: 178.1 ± 7.1 (EG) e 177.7 ± 5.7 (CG) cm; Weight: 76 ± 7.2 (EG) e 79.8 ± 11.9 (CG) kg.	Combat sports (not specified)	Jab; Cross; Front kick; Roundhouse kick.	StrikeMate (DIRA).	Pmean - Jab (7478.82 ± 2994.36 W); Cross (15183.27 ± 4368.90 W); Front kick (7438.64 ± 1910.56 W); Roundhouse kick (45278.30 ± 11323.13 W).
(Del Vecchio et al., 2021)	Cross-sectional	N = 13 men; Age: 28.8 ± 4.57 years; Height: 176.9 ± 4.14 cm; Weight: 80.9 ± 12.24 kg; BMI: 25.9 ± 3.8 kg.m ⁻² .	Combat sports (not specified)	Jab; Cross; Front kick; Roundhouse kick.	StrikeMate (DIRA).	Pmean - Jab (8081 ± 3742 W); Cross (15431 ± 4294 W); Front kick (8563 ± 3095 W); Roundhouse kick (46377 ± 12209 W).

AL = Assessment on the athlete's limb; DIRA = Direct inertia-relevant assessment; EG = Experimental group; CG = Control group; Jab = Straight punch with the front hand; Cross = Straight punch with the back hand; Pmax = Maximum punch power; Pmean = Mean punch power.

Table 3 Assessment of the methodological quality of studies on the impact force of punches

REFERENCE	STUDY DESIGN	BLINDING	REPRESENTATIVITY (SELECTION BIAS)	SAMPLE REPRESENTATIVITY (DROPOUTS)	CONFOUNDING FACTORS	DATA COLLECTION	DATA ANALYSIS	PRESENTATION OF RESULTS	OVERALL CLASSIFICATION
(Adamec et al., 2021)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Buško et al., 2016)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Chadli et al., 2014)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Dunn et al., 2019)	2	3	2	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Dunn et al., 2022)	2	3	2	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Dyson et al., 2005)	2	3	2	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Finlay, 2022)	1	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	strong
(Kim et al., 2018)	1	3	3	1	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Lee & McGill, 2017)	1	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	strong
(Loturco et al., 2016)	2	3	2	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Neto et al., 2009)	2	3	2	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Smith et al., 2000)	2	3	1	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Smith, 2006)	2	3	1	4	3	1	1	1	moderate

(V. A. de Souza & Marques, 2017)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(V. de Souza & Marques, 2017)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Walilko et al., 2005)	2	3	3	4	3	1	1	1	moderate

Legend: 1 = Strong; 2 = Moderate; 3 = Weak; 4 = No rating.

Table 4 Assessment of the methodological quality of studies on the impact power of punches

REFERENCE	STUDY DESIGN	BLINDING	REPRESENTATIVITY (SELECTION BIAS)	SAMPLE REPRESENTATIVITY (DROPOUTS)	CONFOUNDING FACTORS	DATA COLLECTION	DATA ANALYSIS	PRESENTATION OF RESULTS	OVERALL CLASSIFICATION
(Brown et al., 2020)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Brown et al., 2021)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Brown et al., 2022)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Brown et al., 2023)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate
(Del Vecchio et al., 2018)	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	2	moderate
(Del Vecchio et al., 2019)	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	2	moderate
(Del Vecchio et al., 2021)	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	1	moderate

Legend: 1 = Strong; 2 = Moderate; 3 = Weak; 4 = No rating.

4-Discussion

Anthropometric Characteristics

The dynamics of striking combat sports competitions are intrinsically complex and multifaceted, especially when considering the variability in strategies adopted by athletes with different anthropometric characteristics. The essential objective in a striking combat sports competition is to reach the opponent with an effective technical gesture while minimizing the opportunity for immediate counterattack (Beattie & Ruddock, 2022; Dunn et al., 2022).

Punch Impact

Several studies have attempted to identify which punch generates the most impact. However, there is still no clear consensus, likely due to the various variables involved in creating impact (Atha et al., 1985; Girodet et al., 2005; Pierce et al., 2006; Smith, 2006; Tiwari et al., 2021). The absence of a Gold Standard for evaluating punch performance, combined with the variety of assessment instruments and protocols used, has resulted in a wide range of impact force values reported in the literature, varying from 544 to 6860 N (Beattie & Ruddock, 2022; Walilko et al., 2005).

Some studies ($k=6$) presented the maximum impact force (F_{max}) values, while others ($k=10$) reported mean impact force (F_{mean}) values. This disparity in measurements can complicate comparative analysis of the results since F_{max} and F_{mean} offer different perspectives on the impact. Despite these differences, the highest impact force values reported in the literature consistently refer to the mean impact force of the punches. This suggests that mean force has been the preferred measure.

Moreover, the literature indicates that athletes in higher weight categories tend to produce punches with greater impact. However, the punch's impact is not determined solely by weight but also by factors such as strength, technique, speed, limb length, and muscle mass of the athletes (Pierce et al., 2006; Podhurskyi, 2020; Tiwari et al., 2021; Walilko et al., 2005). In this literature review, we could not establish a causal relationship between participants' anthropometric characteristics, such as height, and the observed high or low force values. However, we observed differences in weight that influence some levels of impact force. In the study where participants had a lower mean weight (64.56 ± 12.1 kg), Loturco et al. (2016) reported lower force levels (1331.67 ± 234.49 N) compared to the

study with a higher mean weight (86.8 ± 17 kg), de Souza and Marques (2017), where higher force levels were observed (2260.79 ± 538.44 N).

However, we noted that the study by Loturco et al. (2016) included both men and women in the sample, which may have introduced biases in the results, as men generally exhibit higher punch impact force. On the other hand, the study by Kim et al. (2018) and Smith et al. (2006), which used samples composed only of men and reported similar mean weights of 67.7 kg and 67 ± 10 kg respectively, reported higher force values than those observed in the study by de Souza and Marques (2017). This suggests that weight, while relevant, is not the only characteristic that can influence impact force.

In the same line, and contrary to previous literature that suggest that athletes in higher weight categories tend to produce punches with greater impact, the comparison between weight and impact power, show that the participants in this review with the highest impact power (22014 ± 1336 W) had a lower body weight of 76.5 ± 10 kg. Conversely, participants with higher body weights (80.9 ± 12.2 kg) displayed lower impact power (15431 ± 4294 W). However, it's essential to note that the study involving participants with higher body weights did not specify the type of combat sports they practiced. This could introduce biases in the results. For example, if these individuals are not specialists in punch techniques, as boxers are, their impact power might be lower due to a lack of specific training in this area.

Regarding the relationship between height and impact power, our analysis did not reveal a causal relationship, likely due to the limited variation in height among participants. Participants with a mean height of 178 ± 4 cm demonstrated the highest impact power (22014 ± 1336 W). In contrast, those with slightly greater heights (181.7 ± 8.3 cm) exhibited lower power levels (19640 ± 1410 W), and participants with shorter heights (176.7 ± 6.2 cm) showed even lower power levels (15227 ± 225 W). The difficulty in observing a clear relationship between height and impact power may be attributed to the minimal height differences within the sample, which could have constrained the ability to detect variations.

Furthermore, the studies that analyzed punch power, those focused exclusively on Straight punches. This focus can be explained by the high scientific reliability of the instrument used to analyze the power of Straight punches (linear punches), with an error margin of 0.8% to 3.6%. However, this error margin applies to linear impact, which may

be one of the reasons why the instrument has been used only in studies that analyze Straight punches (Del Vecchio et al., 2022).

To advance the understanding of punch impact, future research should adopt a more comprehensive approach, including a greater diversity of participants' anthropometric characteristics and using validated assessment instruments for different types of punches. This is especially important since some studies demonstrate that Hooks generate more impact than Straight punches (Del Vecchio et al., 2022; Dunn et al., 2019, 2022; Finlay, 2022). The standardization of evaluation protocols and the inclusion of measures for different technical gestures are essential for obtaining a more complete and accurate understanding of punch force and power in striking combat sports.

The studies that validated the PowerKube instrument did so in a way that the evaluation was not adequate for punches that do not have a linear direction. This assumption arises because, although Hook punches are actions performed mainly in lateral movements rather than frontal ones towards the target, at the moment of impact, where contact with the target occurs, the punches do not continue in a lateral direction relative to the target but may have a predominantly linear direction. This can be explained by two main reasons. First, the positioning of the athlete when delivering the punch may be adjusted so that, at the moment of impact, the direction is predominantly linear. If the Hook punch, which is a lateral movement, is executed while the athlete is positioned laterally to the instrument, the geometry of the cube and the trajectory of the punch can result in a linear impact at the moment of contact with the target. This phenomenon can be verified in studies analyzing impact force against force platforms, where the athlete positions themselves laterally to the instrument (Omcirk et al., 2022). Second, the way the PowerKube validation was conducted may have influenced the results. The validation was carried out using an object that collided with the cube at different angles. Despite the method being reliable and having an extremely low error margin (0.35%), it was expected that the further away from the sensors and with a misaligned direction relative to the target, the greater the inconsistency in the results, increasing the error margin, invalidating the possibility of analyzing punches that were not linear. Therefore, it would be interesting to consider an alternative validation method for non-linear movements, such as the Hook, but that hit the target in a more aligned direction, minimizing diagonal impacts. This alternative approach could involve validating the instrument using non-linear punches performed under conditions that more faithfully simulate the context of a competition,

where athletes can adjust their positioning to maximize the linearity of the impact. Such a method would help reduce the error margin and provide more consistent and representative results of the reality of striking combat sports. This type of validation seems fundamental for the development of training strategies and technical improvement for athletes and coaches who want to analyze and improve the performance of non-linear punches.

5 - Limitations

The objective of this review was to reflect on what the literature mentions about anthropometric characteristics and punch impact, but relevant studies with information on each variable may have been excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria. One of the main reasons was the lack of presentation of the participants' anthropometric characteristics and/or the use of different units of measurement to analyze punch impact. According to the literature, various studies have measured punch impact using units such as force (N), power (W), velocity (m/s), acceleration (m/s^2), gravitational acceleration (g), and mass (kg). These units were evaluated with different instruments, such as accelerometers, high-speed cameras, force platforms, load cells, and transducers. This diversity of equipment and measurements complicates the standardization and analysis of results, potentially causing bias. Therefore, only studies with measurements in Newtons (N) and Watts (W) were included.

Due to the homogeneity of the samples, it was not possible to analyze whether there are differences between the type of punch that generates the most impact and height or weight. This lack of diversity may have compromised the ability to detect significant differences in punching strategies between athletes with different anthropometric characteristics.

Another limitation is related to the type of instruments used for analyzing impact force. Since all instruments in the studies reviewed were direct inertia evaluation tools, it was not possible to compare whether the type of instrument could influence the variability of impact force values. However, it was observed that the instrument with the highest mean impact force values was one with a load cell inserted into a wall bag (5008.6 ± 76.3 N), while the lowest values were reported by a target with an accelerometer and load cell (989 ± 116.76 N). Differences in impact on some instruments may be due to the material's inherent resistance, which could influence the dispersion of force caused by the punch

impact. However, these conclusions could not be drawn due to the lack of a standardized method for comparing the data obtained from the different instruments.

6 - Conclusion

The current state of research on anthropometric characteristics and punch impact in striking combat sports shows that this is a complex and multifaceted area that requires further investigation. Although the literature suggests that height may play a crucial role in the choice and effectiveness of punches among athletes, this literature review was unable to confirm this relationship. Despite progress in understanding some aspects related to these variables, significant gaps remain in the literature.

This review highlights the importance of continued investigation into the determinants of striking combat sports performance, with studies that systematically analyze the influence of anthropometric characteristics, standardizing the instruments used to evaluate punch impact to allow for the reliable analysis of different punches. This will contribute to better interpretation of study results and the advancement of striking combat sports.

7 - Future Implications

Future research should include more diverse samples in terms of anthropometric characteristics to better elucidate how those variables influence punch impact.

The standardization of analysis methods and instruments used to measure punch impact force is crucial for advancing research in this area, allowing for comparison of results across different studies and identification of more consistent patterns among different samples.

Additionally, it is important that new validations of instruments analyzing punch power be conducted to identify differences between linear and non-linear punches.

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